

Synthesis of some New Substituted Thiosemicarbazides and Triazoles as Possible Anticonvulsants

M. I. HUSAIN* and MOHD. AMIR

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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Fourteen 1-*o/p*-anisoylacetyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides and their corresponding 5-(*o/p*-anisoxymethyl)-4-aryl-3-mercapto-1,2,4(*H*)-triazoles were synthesised. Eight of these compounds, when screened against maximal electroshock and pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures in mice at a dose of 80 mg/kg were, however, found to be inactive.

VARIOUS hydrazine derivatives¹ and semicarbazides² have been known to inhibit monoamine oxidase activity³. Monoamine oxidase inhibitors have also been reported to exhibit marked anticonvulsant activity⁴. Several mercaptotriazole⁵⁻⁸ derivatives have displayed significant anticonvulsant activity. Moreover, the presence of a methoxy group in a compound imparts anticonvulsant activity. Encouraged with these observations, it is considered worthy to synthesise the title compounds.

An *o/p*-methoxyphenol was allowed to react with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of acetone and anhydrous K₂CO₃ to give ethyl *o/p*-anisoyacetate which was condensed with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol to yield *o/p*-anisoyacetic acid hydrazides. The latter, on being refluxed with various aryl isothiocyanates gave thiosemicarbazides which on cyclisation under alkaline conditions afforded the desired mercaptotriazoles.

TABLE 1—1-*o/p*-ANISOXYACETYL-4-ARYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDE (3)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M. p. °C	Molecular formula	N% : Found/(Calcd.)
1.*	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	Phenyl	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.32 (12.69)
2.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Tolyl	159	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.78 (12.17)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Chlorophenyl	161	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.12 (11.49)
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	3-Chlorophenyl	155	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	10.98 (11.49)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Ethoxyphenyl	162	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.48 (11.20)
6.*	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Anisyl	164	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	11.28 (11.63)
7.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	α-Naphthyl	156	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.46 (11.02)
8.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	Phenyl	150	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.23 (12.69)
9.*	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Tolyl	159	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.54 (12.17)
10.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Chlorophenyl	163-65	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.16 (11.49)
11.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	3-Chlorophenyl	162	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.82 (11.49)
12.*†	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Ethoxyphenyl	163	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ S	11.62 (11.20)
13.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Anisyl	157	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	11.18 (11.63)
14.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	α-Naphthyl	164	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	11.38 (11.02)

*ν_{max} 1 085-1 140 (C-S), 1 600 (Ar), 1 685-1 710 (C=O of sec. amide), 2 900 (CH) and 3 200-3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH).
†τ(CDCl₃) 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃ of OEt), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.95 (2H, q, CH₂ of OEt), 4.55 (2H, s, OCH₂CO), 6.85-7.3 (8H, m, ArH), 7.4 (1H, s, CS-NHAr) and 8.7 (2H, brs, CONHNHCS).

TABLE 2—5-(*o/p*-ANISOXYMETHYL)-4-ARYL-3-MERCAPTO-1,2,4 (H)-TRIAZOLE (4)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M. p. °C	Molecular formula	N% : Found/(Calcd.)
1.*	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	Phenyl	168	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.13 (13.42)
2.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Tolyl	180	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.43 (12.84)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Chlorophenyl	183	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	12.46 (12.08)
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	3-Chlorophenyl	190	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	11.74 (12.08)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Ethoxyphenyl	182	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.18 (11.76)
6.*	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	4-Anisyl	173	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.87 (12.24)
7.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	α -Naphthyl	172	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.12 (11.57)
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	Phenyl	173=175	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.15 (13.42)
9.*†	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Tolyl	179	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.32 (12.84)
10.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Chlorophenyl	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	12.52 (12.08)
11.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	3-Chlorophenyl	172	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	11.75 (12.08)
12.*	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Ethoxyphenyl	168	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.23 (11.76)
13.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	4-Anisyl	181	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.83 (12.24)
14.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	α -Naphthyl	180	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.18 (11.57)

* ν_{max} 1 130 and 1 340 (C=S of amide), 1 600 (Ar), 2 900 (CH) and 3 200-3 300 cm⁻¹. † τ (CDCl₃) 6.65 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.75 (2H, s, NCCH₂), 6.7-7.25 (8H, m, ArH) and 6.33 (1H, brs, SH).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel.

Ethyl ortho/para-anisoxycetates (1): To a solution of *o/p*-methoxyphenol (0.08 M) in anhydrous acetone (25 ml) was added ethyl chloroacetate (0.08 M) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.08 M). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 15 h and then cooled, filtered and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue thus obtained was utilised in the next step without further purification.

Ortho/para-anisoxycetic acid hydrazides (2): A mixture of 1 (0.06 M) and hydrazine hydrate (0.09 M) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 12 h. Excess ethanol was distilled off and the solid mass thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene. The hydrazides thus prepared are (i) *o*-anisoxycetic acid hydrazide (65%), m.p. 80° (Found : N, 13.98. C₉H₁₂N₂O₃ calcd. for : N, 14.28%) and (ii) *p*-anisoxycetic acid hydrazide (60%), m.p. 78°

(Found : N, 13.86. C₉H₁₂N₂O₃ calcd. for : N, 14.28%).

1-ortho/para-anisoxycetyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides (3): A mixture of 2 (0.004 M) and an aryl isothiocyanate (0.004 M) in anhydrous benzene (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3-5 h. Excess benzene was distilled off and the solid product thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The thiosemicarbazides (Table 1) so obtained were characterised by their sharp m.p.'s, elemental analysis and ir spectra.

5-(ortho/para-anisoxymethyl)-4-aryl-3-mercapto-1,2,4 (H)-triazoles (4): A solution of 1-anisoxycetyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazide (3) in 2N NaOH (30 ml) was refluxed for 2-3 h and then filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute HCl. The precipitate formed was collected by filtration, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by their sharp m.p.'s, analysis and ir spectra (Table 2). The peak around 1 700 cm⁻¹ (C=O of sec. amide) observed in the corresponding thiosemicarbazides was absent in these compounds.

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